

**Pouring a polymer into composites
in the vertical direction to
improve the impact resistance property**

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ABSTRACT

In order to improve the impact resistance property of advanced composites, a new technique is tried. A polymer is poured into precured laminate in the vertical direction following a preset pattern, then the uncured polymer is cured to form a laminate composite. Residual strength after drop weight impact (CAI) of the polymer laminate composite is greater by about 14% than that of the conventional laminate composite. The test method used is the SACMA—88 standard method. In addition to the CAI level, the strain at failure also is increased.

Keywords; Damage tolerance

Introduction

Carbon fiber composites have been used to achieve substantial reduction in structural weight of both military and commercial aircraft. These materials have several properties which make them suitable for use in these structures such as high specific stiffness and strength, good fatigue resistance, anti—corrosion and easy processing. However, advanced composites materials are susceptible to damage

when impacted by a solid object. This delamination in turn reduces the strength and stiffness of the material significantly. It is clear that delamination represents the most prevalent life—limiting failure mode in laminated composite structures. Suppression of delamination and enhancement of impact resistance properties have become of very great importance. Recently, a great deal of research has been performed in respect to improving delamination resistance capability. The following several approaches seem to be efficient in this area.

a) Toughening a thermoset matrix or using a thermoplastic matrix^[1] to minimize the interlaminar normal stress of the composite which is the dominant material property controlling the initiation of delamination.

b) Incorporation of discrete layers of a high shear strain thermoplastic resin film as an interleaf at the laminar interfaces^[2]. This provides the composites with ability to undergo higher deformation and avoid damage at low impact energy.

c) Stitching preform laminate structure with dry thread, then impregnating the stitched preform with resin under vacuum^[3]. This is the resin transfer molding (RTM) technique, to prevent delamination and increase laminate residual compression strength after impact effectively.

d) Employing a braiding technique to form an integral structure by intertwining two or more systems of yarns in the bias direction^[4]. This will arrest the spread of delamination under kinetic loading.

Concept of pouring

It is well known that laminate composites are overlaid layer by layer. Therefore, they are connected together by a weak interface of polymer resin, which possess poor impact resistance. The interfaces are inherently weak due to several factors such as stress discontinuity at the interface, absence of high strength fibre reinforcement through the thickness and brittle nature of thermoset matrix. The weak interface induced delamination of the composite when it was impacted by a dynamic body. Obviously, increasing interface strength can restrict delamination, and in turn enhance ability of impact resistance of the composite. From this point of view, stitching and braiding are effective approaches, however they can hardly be used by a real structure such as a special wing struc-

ture. Pouring a special polymer into a composite through its thickness for a resin rail in the vertical direction to prevent delamination from growing at distances far away from the centre of impact. This may be a practical approach for some structures, such as a thin skin and a large area panel.

Advantages of the pouring approach are;

- It can enhance compression strength and strain after impact effectively, but it does not reduce modulus and stiffness of the composite or increase weight.
- It is a reliable method for increasing interlaminar strength. The pouring hole in the composite surface will seal automatically to avoid water and vapour being absorbed.
- The pouring material can match the matrix resin very well, each pouring point is individual. The areas between the pour point did not become loose or tight such as would happen in stitching layers of fabric.
- Ease of operation and inexpensive.

Test and preliminary result

Test Program;

- Pouring material selected
 - • Should match with matrix resin, having same viscosity characteristics.
 - Should co—cure with matrix resin.
 - • can seal hole automatically.
 - • having improved toughness property.
- Pouring technique selected
 - • hand tool
 - • design of machine for production
- Pouring pattern
 - gap between pouring points.
- Develop curing schedule for poured composite in the autoclave.

Comparison of CAI value of poured laminate composite with reference sample is listed in Table 1. (at same impact energy and same size of sample)

Table 1

Pouring pattern (spacing)	CAI strength	CAI strain	short beam short beam shear at 150°C	weight gained
4mm × 4mm	174.1MPa	3550	76.6MPa	0.06%
no	153MPa	3150	76.6MPa	0

Conclusion

It is clear that CAI of treated laminate is 14% greater than that of reference sample. There is no decrease of hot/wet properties and weight increase is kept to a minimum. The preliminary results show that pouring a special resin into advanced composites through the full thickness is a method of practically and effectively enhancing the impact resistance property. If this method is to be optimized, there are possibilities to further enhance the damage tolerance of composites.

References

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